

A Study of Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity of Head Teachers of Primary School

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1. Introduction

Teaching is always a dynamic activity. It unfolds a world of knowledge, information, experience and education. As laid down in the report of International Commission on Education (1996) in any event, no reform can succeed without the co-operation and active participation of teachers. The social, cultural and material status of educators should be considered as a matter of priority. The progress of any country is the only result of the hard-working hand of teacher of the nation, preparing a base for good citizens for the nation. As the there is a place of gardener in the garden, there is a place of teacher in the school. It is the great responsibility carried out by the gardener in the form of teacher to blossom flower in the form of child/students watering and modeling in the form of education by taking a lot of care as the parents, as the teacher called the second parents of the child. In the primary school first stage of the modeling life of children is began in the educational and social life. Moreover, the children of this stage are imitative. They have the idea and different thoughts in their mind that is the truth as stated and done by the teacher by the great way. In the most of the primary school most of the female teachers are serving as the teacher. Therefore, it can be said that if powers lying among female teachers must be prepare in a proper direction, the same may be helpful in development of personality of a person. So, it is very necessary to study the personality traits and characteristics of the female teachers in the various context of personality.

Commission (1964-66) of all the different factors which influence the quality of education and its contribution to national development the quality competence and character of teachers are undoubtedly the most significant. National Policy of Education (1986) also recommended incentives for good teachers. Teachers are considered the most important asset for any institution. Effective teacher is that who has clear standards for classroom behavior, clear and focused instruction, and use effective questioning techniques, provided feedback, and used a variety of assessment strategies. Teachers are the social doctors. Criterion for culturally relevant teaching is nurturing and supporting competence in both home and school cultures. Teachers should use the students' home cultural experiences as a foundation upon which to develop knowledge and skills. Content learned in this way is more significant to the students and facilitates the transfer of what is learned in school to real-life situations. Teachers should encourage such a classroom environment that is inviting, respectful, supportive, inclusive and flexible among students.

2. Title of the study

A Study of Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity of Head Teachers of Primary School

3. Statement of the Problem

Gujarat government presently look forward and organizes various programme for the quality enhancement in primary education in accordance with Right To Education and norms of National Council of Teacher Education and Head teacher of primary school has been upgraded and selected as the 'Principal' in the primary education, in this situation it becomes necessary to study of and Work

Assurance to their Managerial Capacity of Head Teacher of primary school appointed by the HTAT Examination at primary level.

4. Operational definition

In this present study statement defined and to elaborate and focusing on the research study what will be the study will be carried out by its meaning is explored through the operational definitions.

4.1 Primary School

According to the Act of Mumbai Primary Education-1947; Primary school means the school giving primary education of standard one (1) to seven (7). In this present study Primary School means school giving primary education of standard one (1) to eight (8) in Gujarat state according to the RTE-2009. According to GCERT cluster school that leads the school of the nearest seven or more than seven school of area availability of the frequency of the primary teacher.

5. Objectives of the study

To construct and standardize Principal Administrative Rating Scale for the Head Teacher of primary school.

- 1.To construct and standardize Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity Rating Scale for Head Teacher of primary school.
- 2.To study level of Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity of Head Teacher of primary school with reference to gender.
- 3.To study level of Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity of Head Teacher of primary school with reference to habitat.
- 4.To study level of Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity of Head Teacher of primary school with reference to administrative experience and administrative experience.

6. Variables of the study

Variables are the conditions or characteristics that the experimenter manipulates, controls or observes. The following variables were considered in the present study. According to Deepika Shah: “Variable is one of the characteristics that be given value in which reflection characteristics can be seen in individual, group and environment. In this present study Head Teacher in primary school were considered as the control variable of the study. Variables of the present study are given as follows.

Table 1: Variables of the study

Sr.	Types of variables	Variable	Level	Information
1.	Independent	Gender	1.Male 2.Female	Collected Information
		Habitat	1.Rural 2.Urban	Collected Information
		Administrative experience	1.Exp. < 5 Years 2.Exp. > 5 Years	Collected Information
2.	Dependent	Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity		Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity Rating Scale

7. Field of Research

In this present study newly appointed Head teacher of primary school has been upgraded and selected as the ‘Principal’ in the primary education by the Gujarat government for the quality enhancement in primary education. Head Teacher are considered as the field of the research of the study.

8. Types of Research

Research is looking scientific meaningful solution of problems. Generally, there are three types of the research are given as 1) Classical/Causal Research 2) Descriptive research and Action/Relational research. In this present study descriptive type of the research were carried out. Descriptive research used to find out the new knowledge, truth, principle or generalization in new or unknown condition of life.

9. Limitation of Research

Every research could not be always comprehensive. Present research has some the limitation decided with reference to limitation of the research study. In this present research limitation of the present study are given as follows. Present study was delimited only Head Teacher of primary school of who are newly appointed on the basis of HTAT Examination of primary level. Present study was delimited only Head Teacher serving in the primary school of Gujarat during the year of 2017-2018.

10. Significance of Research

Research is one of the specific activities, which is useful and important in the field of education. Educational administrative problems can be solving by the using scientific way research. So, research work is very important. Significance of the present research is follows. Present research was useful to principals of the primary, secondary, higher secondary and the entire educational field at global level and it were useful to study the research studies at national and international level to study the problems of principals. As well as research work were helpful to organization like NCERT, GCERT, DIET to organize various training to the Head Teacher of the primary school of Gujarat State.

11. Research design

Research method is one of the parts of research. To distinguish the efforts between the specifying the research problem and outcomes of the study is known as the research method. Present research is descriptive type in nature. In the descriptive type research relational survey and developmental researches are used. In this present research survey method were used to collect the data.

12. Population and sample

In this present study all the Head Teacher in primary school of the Gujarat State were considered as the population of the study.

13. Selection of the sample

A sample may be defined as a selected number from the population to represent it. Generally, this selection is done according to some rule or plan. For the present study random sampling technique were used to taking sample for the research. In this present study total selected districts of Gujarat state and Head teachers were selected by the stratified quota random sampling for the research purpose. From the present selected fourteen district total 4537 Head Teacher in primary school of the Gujarat State were consider as the sample of the study. By using lottery system one thousand Head Teacher of primary school were selected randomly.

Table 2: Gender wise sample

Gender	Sample
Male	285
Female	75
Total	360

From the Table, is shows that 285 and 75 male and female Head teachers of the primary schools from the North Gujarat were selected for the present study.

14. Tool for the study

Likert type, five-point scale of Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity Rating Scale were prepared by the Investigator to keep in mind the traits of Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity of Head Teachers in the primary school. Positive and negative items were selected and organized in the tool, total necessary items were tested and items were selected for the final try out of the study, finally standardization of tool were carried out by testing reliability and validity of the tool. Statements related to tool were collected and prepared by interviewing the experts and principals of the college. Validity and reliability carried out and tested for the final tool of Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity Rating Scale. Finally prepared tool was applied for the data collection.

15. Hypothesis of the study

Hypothesis of the present study are given as follows.

- H₀₁: There will be no significant difference between mean score of sample of male and female rural habitat having less than 5 years administrative experience Primary School Head Teachers on Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity Rating Scale.
- H₀₂: There will be no significant difference between mean score of sample of rural habitat and urban habitat male having less than 5 years administrative experience Primary School Head Teachers on Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity Rating Scale.
- H₀₃: There will be no significant difference between mean score of sample having less than 5 years and greater than 5 years administrative experience rural habitat male Primary School Head Teachers on Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity Rating Scale.

16. Data Collection

In this present study to study the by the Head Teacher in primary school of the Gujarat State, prior permission was taken from the newly appointed Head Teachers with the help of telephonic communication and then after letter and data were collected through administration of the tool by direct administrating Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity.

17. Data analysis

As the need of the present study data were analyzed with reference to gender, habitat, education stream, category, educational qualification, teaching and administrative experience of Head Teacher of primary school. data were collected and analyzed by using score on tool and with the help of computer Mean, Mode, S.D., Chi-Square Value and t-Value, statistical technique applied to different group of sample for the present study.

18. Major findings of the study

Gender-wise Score of the percentage of frequency of the male and female sample of the Head teachers of the primary schools were found Very Low (180-185) are 3 % and 7 % respectively same as Very High (228-233) are 5 % and 5 % respectively on the work Assurance. Gender wise percentage of male is found higher than the Male Head teachers of the primary schools. From the comparison of group, percentage of group of Male Head teachers of the primary schools were found higher than above female groups.

18.1 Effect of Gender of Primary School Head Teachers on Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity

- Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity of male rural habitat Primary School Head Teachers were not found to be significantly higher than the Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity of female rural habitat Primary School Head Teachers. So, it can be said that gender-wise Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity of male Primary School Head Teachers were not found to be significantly higher than female Primary School Head Teachers.

- Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity of male urban habitat Primary School Head Teachers were not found to be significantly higher than the Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity of female urban habitat Primary School Head Teachers. So, it can be said that gender-wise Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity of male Primary School Head Teachers were not found to be significantly higher than female Primary School Head Teachers.
- Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity of male having less than 5 years administrative experience Primary School Head Teachers were not found to be significantly higher than the Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity of female having less than 5 years administrative experience Primary School Head Teachers. So, it can be said that gender-wise Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity of male Primary School Head Teachers were not found to be significantly higher than female Primary School Head Teachers.
- Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity of male having greater than 5 years administrative experience Primary School Head Teachers were not found to be significantly higher than the Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity of female having greater than 5 years administrative experience Primary School Head Teachers. So, it can be said that gender-wise Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity of male Primary School Head Teachers were not found to be significantly higher than female Primary School Head Teachers.
- Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity of male rural habitat Primary School Head Teachers were not found to be significantly higher than the Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity of female rural habitat Primary School Head Teachers. So, it can be said that gender-wise Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity of male Primary School Head Teachers were not found to be significantly higher than female Primary School Head Teachers.

18.2 Effect of Habitat of Primary School Head Teachers on Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity

- Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity of rural habitat male Head Teachers were not found to be significantly higher than the Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity of urban habitat male Head Teachers. So, it can be said that habitat-wise Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity of rural habitat Primary School Head Teachers were not found to be significantly higher than urban habitat Primary School Head Teachers.
- Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity of rural habitat female Head Teachers were not found to be significantly higher than the Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity of urban habitat female Head Teachers. So, it can be said that habitat-wise Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity of rural habitat Primary School Head Teachers were not found to be significantly higher than urban habitat Primary School Head Teachers.
- Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity of rural habitat having less than 5 years administrative experience Primary School Head Teachers were not found to be significantly higher than the Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity of urban habitat having less than 5 years administrative experience Primary School Head Teachers. So, it can be said that habitat-wise Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity of rural habitat Primary School Head Teachers were not found to be significantly higher than urban habitat Primary School Head Teachers.
- Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity of rural habitat having greater than 5 years administrative experience Primary School Head Teachers were not found to be significantly higher than the Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity of urban habitat having greater than 5 years administrative experience Primary School Head Teachers. So, it can be said that habitat-wise Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity of rural habitat Primary School Head Teachers were not found to be significantly higher than urban habitat Primary School Head Teachers.
- Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity of rural habitat Primary School Head Teachers were not found to be significantly higher than the Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity of urban habitat Primary School Head Teachers. So, it can be said that habitat-wise Work Assurance to their

Managerial Capacity of rural habitat Primary School Head Teachers were not found to be significantly higher than urban habitat Primary School Head Teachers.

18.3 Effect of Experience of Primary School Head Teachers on Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity

- Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity of urban habitat having greater than 5 years administrative experience Primary School Head Teachers were not found to be significantly higher than the Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity of urban habitat having less than 5 years administrative experience Primary School Head Teachers. So, it can be said that experience-wise Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity of Primary School Head Teachers having greater than 5 years administrative experience were found to be significantly higher than Primary School Head Teachers having less than 5 years administrative experience.
- Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity of male having greater than 5 years administrative experience Primary School Head Teachers were not found to be significantly higher than the Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity of male having less than 5 years administrative experience Primary School Head Teachers. So, it can be said that experience-wise Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity of Primary School Head Teachers having greater than 5 years administrative experience were found to be significantly higher than Primary School Head Teachers having less than 5 years administrative experience.
- Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity of female having greater than 5 years administrative experience Primary School Head Teachers were not found to be significantly higher than the Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity of female having less than 5 years administrative experience Primary School Head Teachers. So, it can be said that experience-wise Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity of Primary School Head Teachers having greater than 5 years administrative experience were found to be significantly higher than Primary School Head Teachers having less than 5 years administrative experience.
- Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity of having greater than 5 years administrative experience Primary School Head Teachers were not found to be significantly higher than the Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity of having less than 5 years administrative experience Primary School Head Teachers. So, it can be said that experience-wise Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity of Primary School Head Teachers having greater than 5 years administrative experience were found to be significantly higher than Primary School Head Teachers having less than 5 years administrative experience.

19. Conclusion

From the above research it can be conclude that of group of Male Head teachers of the primary schools were found higher than above female groups, percentage of group of rural habitat Head teachers of the primary schools were found higher than above urban habitat groups, percentage of Head teachers of the primary schools having experience greater than 5 years were found higher than above other groups, there is effect of gender and experience of Primary School Head Teachers were found significant on Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity, gender-wise Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity of male Primary School Head Teachers were not found to be significantly higher than female Primary School Head Teachers, experience-wise Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity of Primary School Head Teachers having greater than 5 years administrative experience were found to be significantly higher than Primary School Head Teachers having less than 5 years administrative experience, there is no any effect of habitat on Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity. So, it can be said that gender and experience of Primary School Head Teachers are the indicators for the Work Assurance to their Managerial Capacity in the school Managerial Capacity.

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